

PDM-2 Factor Structures

Gordon, R.M. (2017). A Concurrent Validity Study of the PDM-2 Personality Syndromes. *Current Psychology*, 1-7, DOI: 10.1007/s12144-017-9644-2

Abstract

This study assessed the concurrent validity of the *Psychodynamic Diagnostic Manual* (PDM-2, APO, 2017) personality syndromes (P Axis) formulation by factor analyzing the countertransference expectation ratings of 412 clinicians of the PDM-2 personality syndromes. This study compared the resulting factor structures of those ratings to some of the leading taxonomies of personality disorders i.e., DSM-5's three personality clusters; levels of personality organization model of Kernberg (1984); internalizing, externalizing, and borderline-dysregulated personality dimensions of the Shedler-Westen Assessment Procedure-II (Westen, Shedler, Bradley, & DeFife, 2012), and the DSM-5's alternative model (American Psychiatric Association, 2013) which uses the Personality Psychopathology Five disorder trait specifiers: negative affectivity, detachment, antagonism, disinhibition, and psychoticism. The results found good concurrent validity for the new PDM-2, P Axis with these leading diagnostic taxonomies. However, it appears that understanding the complexity of personality is not a matter of adding up personality traits as suggested by the DSM-5 Alternative Model.

Key words: countertransference; Psychodynamic Diagnostic Manual-2; personality disorders

PDM-2 Factor Structures

The classification of personality disorders (or the more dimensional conceptualization, personality syndromes) varies from taxonomies and theories. The new Psychodynamic Diagnostic Manual-2 (PDM-2, Alliance of Psychoanalytic Organizations, 2017) personality syndromes (P axis) introduces yet another formulation. How different is it from some of the leading taxonomies of personality disorders? The *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*' (DSM-5 American Psychiatric Association, 2013) uses personality disorder clusters A, B and C. Kernberg (1984) uses levels of personality organization which was further developed by McWilliams (2011a) (neurotic, borderline and psychotic); the Shedler-Westen Assessment Procedure-II (SWAP-II; Shedler & Westen, 2006) found the personality factor structures of: internalizing, externalizing, and borderline-dysregulated, and the DSM-5's alternative model for personality disorders is based on the Five-Factor Model (negative affectivity, detachment, antagonism, disinhibition, and psychoticism).

In 2006, the Psychodynamic Diagnostic Manual (Alliance of Psychoanalytic Organizations, 2006) was published with the goal to be a diagnostic taxonomy that included the complexities of human experience throughout development (both healthy and pathological) and the conceptualization of the major psychological disorders in ways that went beyond external description to the subjective phenomenology and underlying dynamics that shape psychological symptoms and syndromes (Gordon, 2010; McWilliams, 2011b). In contrast to the DSM-5 and ICD-10, the PDM considers the emotional reactions to clients as an important factor in differential diagnosis: "...we also mention the characteristic emotional reactions of therapists when relating to patients with the various personality disorders (i.e., the usual countertransference evoked by the kind of patient in question)." (p. 31).

The Psychodynamic Diagnostic Manual-2 (Alliance of Psychoanalytic Organizations, 2017) maintains the basic structure and assumptions of the PDM-1, while expanding the diagnostic age sections to: Infancy and Early Childhood, Children, Adolescents, Adults, and Elderly.

McWilliams and Shedler (APO, 2017) wrote in the PDM-2, P axis section of adult disorders that countertransference reactions to each of the personality syndromes are important diagnostic indicators. For example, they wrote, "Often, the borderline patient's nonverbal behavior and the therapist's countertransference reactions give more useful information than the patient's verbal communications." (p.26).

The concept of countertransference is complex, evolving from Freud's (1910) early formulation of it due to the patient's influence on the therapist's unconscious feelings, to something that can come from the therapists' own issues, be induced by the patient's behavior, or co-created by the patient and therapist (Gabbard, 2010; Racker, 1957; Tansey & Burke, 2013). Eagle (2000) noted that differential diagnosis of personality organization is informed by transference/countertransference reactions that require the practitioner's insight into his or her own mental states.

Gabbard (2010) emphasizes the centrality of countertransference in the assessment process, noting "Countertransference is now considered a major therapeutic and diagnostic tool that tells the therapist a great deal about the patient's internal world" (p. 15).

PDM-2 Factor Structures

Research has found that transference/countertransference reactions can be helpful to making diagnoses about personality organization (i.e., neurotic, borderline, or psychotic level of organization) and personality disorders (e.g., antisocial, histrionic, narcissistic, etc.) and can also be useful to therapeutic interventions (Betan, Heim, Conklin, & Westen, 2005; Colli, Tanzilli, Dimaggio, & Lingardi, 2014; Gazzillo, et al., 2015; Gordon, et al. 2015; McWilliams, 2011a; Spektor, Luu, & Gordon, 2015).

Comparing the PDM-2 Personality Syndromes to the Other Major Groupings

This study uses the factor structures of clinicians' countertransference ratings of the PDM-2 personality syndromes to the other major personality disorder groupings, theories, and factors structures (i.e., DSM-5's three personality clusters, levels of personality organization, internalizing, externalizing, and borderline-dysregulated personality dimensions, and the Personality Psychopathology Five).

The DSM-5 states, "The personality disorders are grouped into three clusters based on descriptive similarities" (p. 646, American Psychiatric Association, 2013): Cluster A- the "odd, eccentric" cluster: paranoid, schizoid, schizotypal; Cluster B- the "dramatic, emotional, erratic" cluster: antisocial, borderline, histrionic, narcissistic; Cluster C- the "anxious, fearful" cluster: avoidant, dependent, and obsessive-compulsive.

Kernberg (1984) theoretically placed personality organization as a taxon preceding the classification of character or personality syndromes, stating that personality styles can be at the neurotic, borderline (high or low borderline) or psychotic ("severe") levels.

The factor analysis of Westen, Shedler, Bradley, & DeFife (2012), using items from the Shedler-Westen Assessment Procedure-II (SWAP-II; Shedler & Westen, 2006) identified 10 clinically coherent personality diagnoses organized into three higher-order clusters: internalizing, externalizing, and borderline-dysregulated. Westen, Shedler, Bradley, & DeFife, (2012) consider borderline personality disorder as often oscillating between emotions characteristics of both internalizing and externalizing pathology. McWilliams and Shedler (2017) state in the PDM-2 that the P-Axis syndromes are listed in an order consistent with the empirically-identified spectra, "internalizing" and "externalizing." Depressive, dependent, anxious-avoidant, obsessive-compulsive, somatizing, and schizoid are considered in the internalizing personality syndromes, and histrionic, narcissistic, paranoid, psychopathic, and sadistic as the more externalizing personality syndromes.

The DSM-5's alternative model for personality disorders utilizes the research from the Five-Factor Model (Costa & Widiger, 1994) in developing their Personality Psychopathology Five disorder trait specifiers: negative affectivity (e.g., anxiety, depression, guilt, dependency), detachment (e.g., avoidance of socio-emotional experience), antagonism (e.g., egocentricity, entitlement, callous disregard, exploitiveness), disinhibition (e.g., impulsive without regard for consequences), and psychoticism (e.g., odd, eccentric, unusual perceptions, beliefs) (De Fruyt, et al., 2013; Suzuki, Samuel, Pahlen, & Krueger, 2015).

Factor analyses of personality disorders are generally based on personality traits and symptoms from self-reports (De Fruyt, et al., 2013), or lay (Costa & Widiger, 1994) or expert

PDM-2 Factor Structures

raters (Shedler & Westen, 2004). This study however, uses the clinicians' subjective (countertransference) ratings.

Hypotheses

This study tests four hypotheses based on the above discussion of the research.

Hypothesis 1: Factor analyses of practitioners' countertransference expectations of personality organization and personality syndromes should produce factor structures similar to those of the DSM-5 three personality clusters.

Hypothesis 2: Factor analyses of practitioners' countertransference expectations of personality organization and personality syndromes should produce factor structures similar to Kernberg's three levels of personality organization: neurotic, borderline and psychotic.

Hypothesis 3: Factor analyses of practitioners' countertransference expectations of personality organization and personality syndromes should produce factor structures similar to those of the SWAP-II's internalizing, externalizing, and borderline-dysregulated factors.

Hypothesis 4: Factor analyses of practitioners' countertransference expectations of personality organization and personality syndromes should produce factor structures similar to those identified in the Personality Psychopathology Five (negative affectivity (e.g., anxiety, depression, guilt, dependency), detachment (e.g., avoidance of socio-emotional experience), antagonism (e.g., egocentricity, entitlement, callous disregard, exploitiveness), disinhibition (e.g., impulsive without regard for consequences), and psychoticism (e.g., odd, eccentric, unusual perceptions, beliefs).

Method

Instruments

Diagnostic Dimensions and Countertransference (DDC):

The DDC is a survey specifically developed to test our hypotheses. The DDC asked practitioners to rate how much countertransference they think their colleagues would feel to patients from various diagnostic groups. The DDC operationally defines countertransference in simple language. That is, countertransference is operationally defined in this study, in terms of negative feelings so that clinicians of all theoretical orientations can understand it. It asks the practitioner, "Every therapist has at times problematic countertransference reactions (anger, fear, boredom, too much sexual attraction, frustration and dislike). How likely would these diagnostic dimensions affect most therapists' countertransference?" The participant is asked to rate "How strong a countertransference?" (from 1= "None," to 7= "Very Strong") for each of the personality organizations and P axis personality disorders and sub-types.

The survey lists the three levels of personality organization (neurotic, borderline and psychotic) and the 15 P axis personality disorders and sub-types from the PDM-2. The DDC is worded in a projective manner, asking what the practitioner thinks is common to other

PDM-2 Factor Structures

practitioners in order to help control for defensiveness. That is, some therapists might be reluctant to admit that they have countertransference feelings. (See Table 1 for the list of PDM-2 personality syndromes used in this study and the means and standard deviations of the DDC ratings).

Practitioners were provided with written definitions of the three levels of personality organization (neurotic, borderline and psychotic), as well as definitions of the 15 P Axis syndromes and subtypes, both during a workshop with a PowerPoint presentation and in a written handout based on the Psychodiagnostic Chart-2, an instrument for coding the PDM-2 Adult section (Gordon & Bornstein, 2017). Since there were few changes in the list of personality syndromes from PDM-1 to PDM-2, this study used the data from the personality syndromes that were consistent with the PDM-2 P Axis. Both the PDM and PDM-2 include: paranoid, schizoid, psychopathic, hysteric/histrionic, dependent, narcissistic, depressive, somatizing, and sadistic. Masochistic and dissociative were left out of the PDM-2 P Axis, which also combined anxious with phobic/avoidant for the anxious/avoidant/phobic syndrome. The PDM-2 P Axis added borderline personality syndrome, which in this study was labeled “borderline personality organization.”

This simple countertransference measure appears to have acceptable face validity. For example, practitioners rated the psychopathic personality syndrome as likely to have the most expected countertransference ($M = 4.97$, $SD = 2.05$) out of the 15 personality syndromes; while the obsessive-compulsive personality syndrome had the least expected countertransference ($M = 3.12$, $SD = 1.65$) (See Table 1).

Results

Participants and Demographics

We collected data from mandatory continuing education workshops on the topics of diagnostic systems and ethical considerations. The mandatory ethics education requirement helped to produce a large sample of participants from the most common theoretical orientations. Participants were provided a unified and consistent understanding of the operationalized definitions used in the study. Participants were not aware of the hypotheses of the investigation other than that the investigators wanted help in understanding diagnostic issues. In this sample of 412 practitioners, 46% held doctoral degrees, 67% female, mean age was 53.39 ($SD = 14.50$), and their primary orientations were 26% psychodynamic, 33% CBT and 41% other (e.g., family systems, humanistic/existential, and eclectic). In previous research on this sample, we found only one confounding demographic variable with countertransference expectation. Participants with psychodynamic orientations acknowledged stronger countertransference reactions than the participants of other theoretical orientations (Gordon, et al. 2015).

Factor Analysis

For our exploratory factor analysis (EFA), this study used Varimax rotation of 4 factor structures. The theoretical justification for this was to test the concurrent validity of the PDM-2 Adult P axis with other valid personality disorder groupings, most having three or more groupings (e.g., neurotic, borderline, psychotic, Five Personality Factors, etc.).

PDM-2 Factor Structures

We felt that a fourth factor was worth exploring. We accepted a fourth factor since it provided meaningful results while contributing another 4% of the variance (bringing the total percent of the variance covered by the four factors to 76.24%). Using initial Eigenvalues, Factor I accounted for 51% of the variance. Factor II accounted for another 16% of the variance. Factor III accounted for another 6% of the variance, and Factor IV contributed another 4% of the variance. A fifth factor would have only contributed another 3% and little theoretical meaningful results.

We found that both Oblimin rotation, which assumes a fairly high correlation between the factors, and Varimax, which assumes a rather low correlation between the factors, produced similar results. However, since the average correlation between the factors is .349, we decided on an orthogonal rotation (Varimax), which produced the simplest and most distinct solution. Kim & Mueller (1978) suggest theoretical reasons for helping to determine number of factors and type of rotation in exploratory factor analysis. Orthogonal rotation also makes theoretical sense since we are looking at such categorical distinctions as between neurotic, borderline and psychotic personality organizations.

We define complex variables as ones that have the highest loading in one factor, but also have a close high loading in other factors as well. For example, histrionic personality loads mainly on the neurotic factor (.662), but also has a high loading on the borderline factor (.511).

Results of Factor Analysis

Hypothesis 1 was highly supported. Factor analyses of practitioners' countertransference expectations of personality organization and personality syndromes produced three factor structures similar to the DSM-5 Three Personality Clusters. Cluster A (paranoid, schizoid, schizotypal) is very similar to our Factor IV (psychotic level). Factor IV loaded with psychotic personality organization (.649), paranoid (.708) and schizoid (.744).

Cluster B (antisocial, borderline, histrionic and narcissistic) is very similar to our Factor II (borderline level). Borderline personality organization (.713), psychopathic (.712), histrionic (.511) and narcissistic (.753) loaded on Factor II. Histrionic however loaded more on Factor I (.662), indicating the PDM-2 distinction that the hysterical personality is more organized at the neurotic level, and the histrionic personality is more organized at the borderline level. The histrionic personality is more likely to use more primitive defenses than the hysterical personality.

Cluster C (Avoidant, dependent, and obsessive-compulsive) is very similar to our Factor I (neurotic level). Neurotic personality organization (.739), anxious (.888), dependent (.790) and obsessive-compulsive (.777) loaded on Factor I. (See Table 2).

Hypothesis 2 was highly supported. Factor analyses of practitioners' countertransference expectations of personality organization and personality syndromes produced three factor structures similar to Kernberg's three levels of personality organization: neurotic, borderline and psychotic. Neurotic personality organization (.739), depressive (.817), dependent (.790), anxious (.888), obsessive-compulsive (.777), somatizing (.720), and histrionic (.662) loaded on Factor I (Neurotic level). Borderline personality organization (.713), passive-aggressive

PDM-2 Factor Structures

(.738), narcissistic (.753), psychopathic (.712), sadistic (.759) and histrionic (.511) loaded on Factor II (Borderline level). Psychotic personality organization (.649), schizoid (.744), paranoid (.708) loaded on Factor IV (Psychotic level). (See Table 2).

Hypothesis 3 was mainly supported. Factor analyses of practitioners' countertransference expectations of personality organization and personality syndromes produced two factor structures similar to the Internalizing (depressive, dependent, anxious-avoidant, obsessive-compulsive, somatizing, and schizoid) and the Externalizing factors (hysterical-histrionic, narcissistic, paranoid, psychopathic, and sadistic). Depressive, dependent, anxious, obsessive-compulsive, somatization loaded on Factor I, in agreement with the internalizing personality syndromes, except that histrionic loads with both Factor I (internalizing) and Factor II (externalizing), and though schizoid did load on Factor I (.419), it loaded more on Factor IV (psychotic level). Hysterical-histrionic, narcissistic, paranoid, psychopathic, and sadistic had high loading on Factor II. However, paranoid only loaded moderately on Factor II (borderline level, .390), and moderately on Factor I (neurotic level, .390), and mainly on Factor IV (psychotic level, .708). The SWAP II factor-borderline-dysregulated does correspond to Factor III (borderline level). (See Table 2).

Hypothesis 4 was mainly supported. Factor analyses of practitioners' countertransference expectations of personality organization and personality syndromes produced factor structures similar to the the five-factor model or the Personality Psychopathology Five of: negative affectivity (e.g., anxiety, depression, guilt, dependency), detachment (e.g., avoidance of socio-emotional experience), antagonism (e.g., egocentricity, entitlement, callous disregard, exploitiveness), disinhibition (e.g., impulsive without regard for consequences), and psychoticism (e.g., odd, eccentric, unusual perceptions, beliefs). Factor I is similar to the negative affectivity factor: neurotic personality organization (.739), anxiety (.888), depression (.817), and dependency (.790). Factor II is similar to the antagonism factor: borderline personality organization (.713), passive-aggressive (.738), narcissistic (.753), psychopathic (.712), and sadistic (.759). Factor III is similar to the disinhibition factor: hypomanic (.817), counter-dependent (.606), and counter-phobic (.774). Factor IV is similar to the psychoticism factor: psychotic personality organization (.649), schizoid (.744), and paranoid (.708). We did not use a fifth factor in our factor analysis, therefore we were not able to determine a correspondence with the PPF factor of detachment. (See Table 2).

Discussion

This may be the first empirical study of the new PDM-2 Personality Syndromes Adult classification system (P axis). This study found excellent concurrent validity for the PDM-2, P Axis with other major personality syndrome groupings, theories and factors. The P axis syndromes formed four factors that highly corresponded to: 1. the DSM-5 three personality clusters (A, B and C); 2. The three levels of personality organization: neurotic, borderline and psychotic; 3. the internalizing, externalizing dimensions and borderline-dysregulated factors of the SWAP II, and 4. the Personality Psychopathology Five factor traits used in DSM-5 alternative personality disorder model.

PDM-2 Factor Structures

The four factor structures of this study were labeled “neurotic level,” “borderline level,” “impulse problems,” and “psychotic level.” However, also as predicted by McWilliams and Shedler in the Adult P axis section, the constructs are complex and although it could be expected that some personality syndromes such as the hysterical/histrionic styles are more likely to be organized at a neurotic level and those with paranoid or psychopathic styles are more likely to be organized at a borderline or psychotic level, most the personality syndromes can be found at any level of personality organization. Histrionic loaded .662 on the neurotic factor, and .511 on the borderline factor which is consistent the with PDM-2 distinction between hysterical being more organized at the neurotic level and histrionic more organized at the borderline level. Paranoid loaded mostly on the psychotic factor (.708), but also had modest loadings on the neurotic (.390) and borderline (.367) factors, indicating that this style can be found at several levels of personality organization. The same is true with psychopathic personality, which loads strongly on the borderline factor (.712), but has a modest loading on the psychotic factor (.483).

This empirical study used clinicians’ expected countertransference reactions that yielded factor structures very similar to what was found using personality symptoms and traits from self-reports and lay and expert ratings. This finding supports the PDM-2 assumption of the importance of clinicians’ countertransference reactions to their patients as a significant diagnostic tool.

The limitations of this study are that although the respondents were a theoretically diverse group, they were not randomly picked for this study. These findings should be compared to other samples, with other sampling methods. This study uses a limited measure of countertransference (i.e. negative feelings) when countertransference includes a complex range of affects. This study was not about the complexities of countertransference, but only used clinicians’ negative affects to understand their reactions to personality syndromes. This operational definition was used to be understandable to those clinicians who were unfamiliar with the complexities of countertransference and psychodynamic theory. For the sake of this study, this limited definition of countertransference was found to have validity (see table 1). Also, factor analysis is a useful tool for testing certain hypotheses, such as assessing concurrently validity. This study’s findings worked well to provide evidence that the PDM-2 personality syndrome assumptions have excellent concurrent validity with other recognized assessments. However, the tools of categorical statistical analysis are limited when considering psychodynamic assumptions of interdependent, interacting and complex variables. Understanding the complexity of personality is not a matter of adding up personality traits as suggested by the DSM-5 Alternative Model.

Further research is needed to study the construct validity of the P axis syndromes, and if the personality domains of the new PDM-2 adequately cover the array of personality syndromes and their sub-forms found in clinical and forensic practice.

PDM-2 Factor Structures

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Participation was voluntary. Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study. The IRB of Chestnut Hill College determined that this project adequately protects the welfare, rights, and privacy of human subjects. All the participants were given informed consent, right to withdraw, confidentiality/anonymity and there was no deception in this study or any potential risk to participants. All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. The Author declares that he has no conflict of interest.

PDM-2 Factor Structures

References

- Alliance of Psychoanalytic Organizations (2006). *Psychodynamic diagnostic manual*. Silver Spring, MD: Author.
- Alliance of Psychoanalytic Organizations (2017). *Psychodynamic diagnostic manual, Version 2 (PDM-2)*. New York: Guilford Press.
- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (DSM-5®)*. American Psychiatric Pub.
- Betan, E., Heim, A. K., Conklin, C. Z., & Westen, D. (2005). Countertransference phenomena and personality pathology in clinical practice: An empirical investigation. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, *162*, 890–898. doi:10.1176/appi.ajp.162.5.890
- Colli, A., Tanzilli, A., Dimaggio, G., & Lingiardi, V. (2014). Patient personality and therapist response: an empirical investigation. *The American Journal of Psychiatry*, *171*(1), 102–8. doi:10.1176/appi.ajp.2013.13020224
- Costa Jr, P. T., & Widiger, T. A. (1994). *Personality disorders and the five-factor model of personality*. American Psychological Association.
- De Fruyt, F., De Clercq, B., De Bolle, M., Wille, B., Markon, K., & Krueger, R. F. (2013). General and maladaptive traits in a five-factor framework for DSM-5 in a university student sample. *Assessment*, 1073191113475808.
- Eagle, M. N. (2000). A critical evaluation of current conceptions of transference and countertransference. *Psychoanalytic Psychology*, *17* (1), 24, doi:10.1037/0736-9735.17.1.24
- Freud, S. (1910). The Future Prospects of Psychoanalytic Therapy. Standard Edition 11.
- Gabbard, G. O. (2010). *Long-term Psychodynamic Psychotherapy: A Basic Text* (Second Ed.). American Psychiatric Pub.
- Gazzillo, F., Lingiardi, V., Del Corno, F., Genova, F., Bornstein, R. F., Gordon, R. M., & McWilliams, N. (2015). Clinicians' emotional responses and Psychodynamic Diagnostic Manual adult personality disorders: A clinically relevant empirical investigation. *Psychotherapy*, *52*(2), 238.
- Gordon, R.M. (2010). The Psychodynamic Diagnostic Manual (PDM). In I. Weiner and E. Craighead, (Eds.) *Corsini's Encyclopedia of Psychology* (4th ed., volume 3, 1312-1315), Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley and Sons.

PDM-2 Factor Structures

- Gordon, R.M. & Bornstein, R.F. (2017, in press). Construct Validity of the Psychodiagnostic Chart: A Transdiagnostic Measure of Personality Organization, Personality Syndromes, Mental Functioning, and Symptomatology. *Psychoanalytic Psychology*, DOI: 10.1037/pap000014
- Gordon, R.M., Gazzillo, F., Blake, A., Bornstein, R.F., Etzi, J., Lingardi, V., McWilliams, N., Rothery, C. and Tasso, A.F. (2015). The Relationship Between Theoretical Orientation and Countertransference Awareness: Implications for Ethical Dilemmas and Risk Management, *Clinical Psychology & Psychotherapy*, 23, 236-245
- Kernberg, O. F. (1984). *Object Relations Theory and Clinical Psychoanalysis*. Jason Aronson.
- Kim, J. O., & Mueller, C. W. (1978). *Introduction to factor analysis: What it is and how to do it*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
- McWilliams, N. (2011a). *Psychoanalytic Diagnosis, Second Edition: Understanding Personality Structure in the Clinical Process*. Guilford Press.
- McWilliams, N. (2011b). The Psychodynamic Diagnostic Manual: An effort to compensate for the limitations of descriptive psychiatric diagnosis. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 93, 112–122. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00223891.2011.542709>
- McWilliams, N. & Shedler, J. (2017) Personality Syndromes P Axis, In Psychodynamic Diagnostic Manual-2, Edited by Lingardi, V. & McWilliams, Guilford Press.
- Racker, H. (1957). The meanings and uses of countertransference. *The Psychoanalytic Quarterly*, 26(3), 303–57.
- Shedler, J. & Westen, D. (2006). Personality diagnosis with the Shedler-Westen Assessment Procedure (SWAP): Bridging the gulf between science and practice. In PDM Task Force (Ed.), *Psychodynamic Diagnostic Manual*. Silver Spring, MD: Alliance of Psychoanalytic Organizations.
- Shedler, J., & Westen, D. (2004). Dimensions of personality pathology: an alternative to the five-factor model. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 161(10), 1743-1754.
- Spektor, V., Luu, L. & Gordon, R.M. (2015) The Relationship between Theoretical Orientation and Accuracy of Countertransference Expectations., *Journal of the American Psychoanalytic Association*, 63(4), NP28-NP32.
- Suzuki, T., Samuel, D. B., Pahlen, S., & Krueger, R. F. (2015). DSM-5 alternative personality disorder model traits as maladaptive extreme variants of the five-factor model: An item-response theory analysis. *Journal of abnormal psychology*, 124(2), 343.

PDM-2 Factor Structures

Tansey, M. J., & Burke, W. F. (2013). *Understanding Countertransference: From Projective Identification to Empathy*. Routledge.

Westen, D., Shedler, J., Bradley, B., & DeFife, J. A. (2012). An empirically derived taxonomy for personality diagnosis: Bridging science and practice in conceptualizing personality. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 169 (3), 273-284.

PDM-2 Factor Structures

Table 1: Means and Standard Deviations of Practitioners Ratings of Expected Countertransference (CT) to Prototypic Patients' Personality Organization (Neurotic, Borderline, Psychotic) and PDM-2 Personality Syndromes (Depressive, Dependent, etc.)

How much expected CT?	N	Mean CT	Std. Deviation
Neurotic Personality Org	411	3.21	1.52
Borderline Personality Org	412	5.21	1.75
Psychotic Personality Org	412	3.93	1.91
Depressive	411	3.21	1.65
Hypomanic	411	3.71	1.62
Dependent	410	3.73	1.80
Passive-aggressive	410	4.57	1.74
Counter-dependent	410	3.93	1.68
Anxious	410	3.14	1.64
Counter-phobic	409	3.19	1.53
Obsessive-compulsive	410	3.12	1.65
Schizoid	410	3.30	1.86
Somatizing	411	3.20	1.70
Histrionic	410	3.80	1.95
Narcissistic	411	4.91	1.78
Paranoid	411	3.77	1.87
Psychopathic	411	4.97	2.05
Sadistic	411	4.90	2.11

The DDC survey asked, “How likely would these diagnostic dimensions affect most therapists’ countertransference?” The response range was from 1= none, to 7= very strong negative countertransference for each of the 18 variables. The strongest negative CT was to the Psychopathic personality (4.97), and the least negative CT was to the Obsessive-compulsive personality (3.12). These results support the validity of the DDC for showing the understandable differences in CT to the various personality organizations and syndromes.

PDM-2 Factor Structures

Table 2: Personality Organization (Neurotic, Borderline, Psychotic) and PDM-2 Personality Syndromes (Depressive, Dependent, etc.) Factor Structures Based on Expected Countertransference Ratings

Personality Organization and PDM-2 Personality Syndromes	Factor Component			
	I Neurotic Level	II Borderline Level	III Impulse Problems	IV Psychotic Level
Neurotic	.739	.051	.049	.203
Borderline	.169	.713	.312	.299
Psychotic	.124	.377	.381	.649
Depressive	.817	-.041	.253	.157
Hypomanic	.088	.311	.817	.158
Dependent	.790	.405	.007	.010
Passive-agg	.363	.738	.388	.075
Ct-depend	.308	.517	.606	.077
Anxious	.888	-.087	.192	.065
Ct-phobic	.209	.300	.774	.189
Obs-compul	.777	.180	.133	.235
Schizoid	.419	.261	.079	.744
Somatizing	.720	.371	.096	.144
Histrionic	.662	.511	.066	.184
Narcissistic	.247	.753	.280	.263
Paranoid	.390	.367	.123	.708
Psychopath	-.008	.712	.267	.483
Sadistic	-.044	.759	.291	.421

N = ranges from 409-412. Factor I (Neurotic Level) loads with Neurotic Personality Organization, Depressive, Dependent, Anxious, Obsessive-compulsive, Somatizing, and Histrionic. Factor II (Borderline Level) loads with Borderline Personality Organization, Passive-aggressive, Narcissistic, Psychopathic and Sadistic. Factor III (Impulse Problems) loads with Hypomanic, Counter-dependent, and Counter-phobic. Factor IV (Psychotic Level) loads with Psychotic Personality Organization, Schizoid, and Paranoid.